

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**PSYCHOSOCIAL FACTORS CAUSING DEPRESSION DURING
ANTENATAL PERIOD AND THEIR ASSOCIATION WITH
PROGRESSION OF PREGNANCY**¹Dr Bakht Zia, ²Dr Aqsa Maryam Marith, ³Dr Subhan Shahid,¹WMO, Bilal Hospital, Rawalpindi.²WMO, THQ Hospital Wazirabad,³Demonstrator, M.Islam Medical College, Gujrawala.**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine causes and risk factors leading to depression and mood swings among pregnant females visiting antenatal clinics of teaching hospitals in Lahore, Pakistan. **Methodology:** 907 pregnant females were included in study, from antenatal clinics of teaching hospitals in Lahore, Pakistan during January to December 2016. Study follows descriptive, cross-sectional design. Demographic profile was recorded on a questionnaire. The measurement tool for depression was Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics, linear regression and Chi-square test. **Results:** The women with mean age 26.4 ± 4.4 were included in study. 80.5% females had depression during antenatal period. Depression score was calculated in each trimester and it was 67.9%, 83.5% and 85.8% respectively. There was significant increase in depression as pregnancy progresses (P value 0.001). The regression analysis showed the risk factors, patient's education (OR 4.67, 95% confidence interval, 1.97 to 11.07), husband's education (OR 4.67, 95% CI, 1.9 to 11.07), husband's employment (OR 4.67, 95% CI, 1.9 to 11.07), family size (OR 4.67, 95% CI, 1.9 to 11.07), History of miscarriages (OR 4.67, 95% CI, 1.9 to 11.07), number of pregnancies (OR 4.67, 95% CI, 1.9 to 11.07). **Conclusion:** Depression is quite common among females during antenatal period, which increases as pregnancy progresses. The risk factors responsible for it are husband and wife's education, family size, number of pregnancies, history of abortions, monthly income and family financial status. Screening and diagnosis of depression and provision of special care to patient improves the healthy progression of pregnancy.

Key Words: depression, pregnancy, females, causes.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Bakht Zia,
WMO,
Bilal Hospital,
Rawalpindi

QR code

Please cite this article in press Bakht Zia et al., *Psychosocial Factors Causing Depression during Antenatal Period and Their Association with Progression of Pregnancy*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Depression among pregnant females has lead to several negative outcomes on mother and child health. The estimation of prevalence of this problem and the factors causing it are understudy around the globe. Scientist are paying attention towards measuring the extent of this problem in different countries and to figure out the ways to overcome the factors responsible for it in order to improve maternal and child health[1,3].

By keeping in view several studies done on this topic in past it has been observed that most common risk factors associated with this problem are alcoholism, poor social support, less public awareness, male dominance, domestic violence, history of miscarriages, family size, poverty etc [2].

Verbeek T, et al. in his study mentioned that 41% females suffer anxiety during pregnancy while depression rate is 57%, which is quite alarming[2]. In a rsearch study conducted on British Pakistani women, the depression amongst pregnant females was 16.8%[3].

In our culture, depression among pregnant females is far less than in Europe, due to our cultural norms and family support, mothers can share their stress with family members. It has been noticed that single mothers suffer this issue more commonly than those who live with family and in Asian culture [3]. However, both European and Asian societies have different risk factors leading to this cause. As Pakistan is a developing country, it's major problem is unemployment, Malnutrition, poor monthly family income, Desire to get a male child people avoid using family planning measures leading to inadequate spacing between pregnancies, domestic violence, male dominance, large family sizes, maternal education and awareness about maternal and child health is poor, inadequate provision of healthcare facilities etc. [4] Therefore, need was felt to figure out and estimate the prevalence of depression among pregnant females in Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

907 pregnant females who visited antenatal clinics of teaching hospital of Lahore were studied by following descriptive, cross sectional study design.

The study duration was from January to December 2016. Patients without any prior history of depression or psychic disorder before pregnancy, not taking any antipsychotic or anti-depressants, pregnancy is not high risk, without history of any loved one's death in last year, non-addict to alcohol or any drug. The proforma designed for collection of information was divided into two parts. First part had demographic information about patients, second part had information about possible risk factors for depression that is, educational status, family income, number of children, number of pregnancy, abortion history. Another questionnaire was Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). According to this inventory different scores are allotted to patients and depression status is judged in comparison to each score.

Table 1: Beck Depression Inventory scoring.

Score	Depression
0 to 15	Absent
16 to 30	Mild
31 to 45	Moderate
46 to 63	Severe

SPSS 18 was used for data analysis. Linear regression and chi-square tests were applied to predict associated factors for depression.

RESULTS:

Mean age group of understudy population was 27.7 ± 4.8 years, age range was 17 to 45 years. Average marital age was 21.1 ± 4.08 years. 76% population was in urban areas. Mostly women had passed high school examination 42.7% and were house wives (90%). 80.5% husbands were employed, and were earning well. 39% had high school education. 50.4% population already had kids while 47.7% suffered abortion during first trimester. 86% females got pregnant without taking any medicines. 59.9% had normal child birth. 46.1% females had mild depression, 27.2% moderate, 7.2% had severe depression, 19.5% had no depression. The association of degree of depression with the trimester was calculated, it was found out that depression increases as pregnancy progresses. The linear regression results with independent variables clearly depicted that these are the risk factors for depression among pregnant females.

Table: 2 Comparison of depression in all trimesters.

Trimesters	N=907				P value 0000 is p value Df 2 X ² 33.8
	Yes		No		
	N	Percentage	N	Percentage	
First	171	67.9	81	32.1	
Second	193	83.5	38	16.5	
Third	351	85.8	58	14.2	
Total	730	80.5	177	19.5	

Table: 3 Risk factors of depression.

	N in percentages	B	SE	P	OR	CI=95%
Educational level					2.12	2.22-3.63
uneducated	0.9% (8)	.75	.28	.007		
primary	20.9% (190)					
Secondary	42.7% (387)					
Graduated	35.5% (322)					
Husband's education		.04	.02	.01	1.24	.3 to 1.34
Uneducated	1.4% (13)					
Primary	33.7% (306)					
Secondary	38.9% (353)					
Graduated	25.9% (235)					
Husband's job status		.73	13.9	0.00	15.9	3.6 to 65.8
Earning	80.6% (731)					
Not earning	19.4% (176)					
Family size		1.34	0.60	.02	.7	.7 to 1.2
0	51.9% (470)					
1 to 3	45.5% (414)					
More than 3	2.5% (23)					
pregnancy		1.25	.48	.006	2.81	1.3 to 5.7
First	48.5% (440)					
Second	37.2 % (337)					
Third	14.3 % (130)					
Abortion history		16.1	.24	.000	3.9	2.2 to 7.0
Present	22.55 (204)					
Absent	77.5% (703)					

DISCUSSION:

Fan F, et al conducted a survey study on Chinese population and effect on maternal stress on child heart rate and blood pressure was studied. It was noticed that fetal stress is associated with maternal stress and such offspring are more prone to suffer long term cardiovascular problems [6]. Prevalence of depression among pregnant females was studied on Brazil population and it was 14%, according to a survey study conducted in 2009 by Pereira PK, et al [10] Similar studies have been conducted by many authors world wide [8,9].

In our culture, depression among pregnant females is far less than in Europe, due to our cultural norms and family support, mothers can share their stress with family members. It has been noticed that single mothers suffer this issue more commonly than those who live with family and in Asian culture. However, both European and Asian societies have different risk factors leading to this cause [5,7]. As Pakistan is a developing country, it's major problem is unemployment, Malnutrition, poor monthly family income, Desire to get a male child people avoid using family planning measures leading to inadequate spacing between pregnancies, domestic violence,

male dominance, large family sizes, maternal education and awareness about maternal and child health is poor, inadequate provision of healthcare facilities etc. therefore, need was felt to figure out and estimate the prevalence of depression among pregnant females in Pakistan.

CONCLUSION:

Depression is quite common among females during antenatal period, which increases as pregnancy progresses. The risk factors responsible for it are husband and wife's education, family size, number of pregnancies, history of abortions, monthly income and family financial status. Screening and diagnosis of depression and provision of special care to patient improves the healthy progression of pregnancy.

REFERENCES:

- 1- Aktas S, et al. Factors affecting depression during pregnancy and the correlation between social support and pregnancy depression. *Iran Red Crescent Med J* 2015; 17: 9.
- 2- Verbeek T, et al. Anxiety and depression during pregnancy in Central America: a cross sectional study among pregnant women in developing country Nicaragua. *BMC Psychiatry* 2015; 15: 292.
- 3- Husain N, et al. Social stress and depression during pregnancy and in the post natal period in British Pakistani mothers: a cohort study. *Journal of Affective Disorder* 2012; 140 (3): 268-276.
- 4- Silva MMJ, et al. Anxiety in pregnancy; prevalence and associated factors. *Journal of School of Nursing* 2017; 51.
- 5- Kleanthi G. Psychosocial risk factors of depression in pregnancy: a survey study. *Health Science Journal* 2017.
- 6- Fan F, Zou Y, Zhang Y, et al. Effects of maternal anxiety and depression during pregnancy in Chinese women on children's heart rate and blood pressure response to stress. *Journal of human hypertension* 2016; 30: 171-176.
- 7- Vigod SN, et al. Depression in pregnancy. *TheBMJ* 2016; 352.
- 8- Omidvar S, et al. Association of psychosocial factors with pregnancy healthy lifestyles *PLOS* 2018.
- 9- Silva MM, et al. Depression in pregnancy; prevalence and association factors *Invest. Edu. Enform* 2016;34: 2.
- 10- Pereira PK, et al. Depression during pregnancy; prevalence and risk factors among women attending a public health clinic in Reo de Jeneiro, Brazil. *Cad. Saudi. Publica* 2009; 25: 12.